

The Mediating Role of Organizational Exclusion in the Effect of Perceived Organizational Justice on Turnover Intention: A Study on Turkish Employees in Germany

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Abstract

Keywords:

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In this study, the influence of perceived organizational justice on turnover intention, which has become an important issue in working relationships, and the mediating role of perceived organizational exclusion in this relationship are examined. In this direction, a survey was conducted on Turkish employees in various food factories in Lübeck, a German city in the state of Schleswig Holstein, through the purposive sampling method. The obtained data were analyzed with the SPSS quantitative data analysis program. Upon analyzing, it was determined that the perception of organizational justice has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, whereas the perception of organizational exclusion doesn't mediate this relationship. In addition, it was found that employees' perceptions of organizational justice negatively affect their perceptions of organizational exclusion, while organizational exclusion has no significant effect on turnover intention. Finally, the conclusions were addressed in terms of both theoretical and practical contributions, and some advice was given for future researchers and the sector.

Algılanan Örgütsel Adaletin İşten Ayrılma Niyeti Üzerindeki Etkisinde Örgütsel Dışlanmanın Aracı Rolü: Almanya'da Çalışan Türk İşçiler Üzerine Bir Araştırma

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Örgütsel Adalet,
İşten Ayrılma Niyeti,
Örgütsel Dışlanma

Bu araştırmada, algılanan örgütsel adaletin çalışma ilişkilerinde önemli bir konu haline gelen işten ayrılma niyeti üzerindeki etkisi ve algılanan örgütsel dışlanmanın bu ilişkideki aracı rolü incelenmiştir. Bu doğrultuda amaçlı örnekleme yöntemiyle Almanya'nın Schleswig Holstein eyaletinde bulunan Lübeck kentindeki çeşitli gıda fabrikalarında çalışan Türk işçiler üzerinde anket yapılmıştır. Elde edilen veriler SPSS nicel veri analiz programıyla analiz edilmiştir. Analiz sonucunda örgütsel adalet algısının işten ayrılma niyeti üzerinde negatif ve anlamlı bir etkiye sahip olduğu, buna karşın örgütsel dışlanma algısının bu ilişkiye aracılık etmediği bulunmuştur. Ayrıca çalışanların örgütsel adalet algılarının örgütsel dışlanma algularını olumsuz yönde etkilediği; örgütsel dışlanmanın ise işten ayrılma niyeti üzerinde anlamlı bir etkisi olmadığı tespit edilmiştir. Analiz sonuçları teorik ve pratik katkılar bakımından irdelenmiş ve sektöre ve gelecek araştırmacılara yönelik bazı önerilerde bulunulmuştur.

INTRODUCTION

The realization of the desired objectives and being competitive in today's businesses can only be accomplished with happy employees in healthy organizations. This is because the prerequisite for employees to identify with their organization and be connected to it is that they do not encounter negative situations such as job alienation, organizational loneliness, mobbing, organizational injustice and organizational exclusion. Such negativities arising from the employee or the organization directly affect the effectiveness and efficiency of the business and can lead to employee turnover. The point to be considered here is to identify the behaviors that negatively affect the employee and thus the organization, to investigate their causes, and to try to reduce the effects of these behaviors on both employees and the organization or to eliminate them completely.

To be more clearly stated; organizational justice perceived as low in an organization decreases employees' performance and devotion to the organization, and as a result, the perception of organizational exclusion emerges or the tendency to leave the job increases (Özer and Günlük, 2010; İzci, 2018). On the other hand, being excluded from an organization has a negative connotation which can subsequently impact other forms of organizational behavior resulting in negative consequences for the organization and the employee. Since as a result of the disintegration of the employee's relations with supervisors, communication with other representatives and social relations, and as a result of being ignored or disregarded, workers lose their regard and believe in their employments, colleagues, supervisors, and organizations and proposed to stopped their occupations by encountering critical issues (Haq, 2014; Lyu and Zhu, 2019).

As a result of the information obtained from the literature review, it has been revealed that the perception of organizational justice and exclusion have significant effects on turnover intention, and these variables are in direct or indirect relationship and interaction (Özer and Günlük, 2010; Haq, 2014; İzci, 2018; Lyu and Zhu, 2019; Mengstie, 2020; Anthoniammal et al., 2022). However, when this information in the literature is evaluated, there is no study found in which organizational justice, turnover intention, and organizational exclusion variables are examined together. It is thought that this study, in which these three variables are investigated together, will contribute to expanding and enriching the subject in a relational context. In this context, the research is guided by the question "Does the perception of organizational exclusion have a mediating role in the effect of organizational justice on turnover intention?". Therefore, the concepts of organizational justice and organizational exclusion, which cause turnover intention and which are frequently encountered among organizational behavior issues, are discussed as the main elements of this study. As a matter of fact, in this study, organizational justice, organizational exclusion, and turnover intention were discussed. The aim of this study is to examine the effect of organizational justice perception on turnover intention and the mediating role of organizational exclusion on this effect. In addition, determining the effect of organizational exclusion on turnover intention was determined as a sub-objective of this study. In line with the determined purposes, a model was proposed and the model was tested based on the traditional approach.

The cosmopolitan structures of countries make it necessary for people of various nationalities to work together. The fact that individuals who work together and share common interests have different religions, languages, and ethnicities sometimes leads to the exclusion of minorities in the workplace. It is thought that this situation may also be valid for Germany, where a significant portion of the working population consists of foreign employees. The lack of a model proposal that addresses the relevant variables in the sample of Turkish employees in Germany made it necessary to conduct such a study. Therefore, it is believed that this will contribute theoretically and methodologically to the field of business and management and will benefit Germany's foreign worker policies in practice. In addition, a study that addresses organizational justice, organizational exclusion, and turnover intention is important for organizations to effectively manage their

employees and ensure sustainable success. The results of such studies can be used to positively influence the employees' experiences and prevent unintended consequences by guiding the organization's management.

In the research, first of all, the concepts were explained, the relationships among the variables were revealed on the basis of the literature, and hypotheses were developed. At that point, information about the method was given and the research findings were acquired using the SPSS quantitative data analysis program. After the interpretation of the findings, in the conclusion part, theoretical and practical contributions of the study were discussed and some suggestions were made for future research.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Organizational Justice and Turnover Intention

Organizational justice is a concept developed to bring up the importance of justice in the organization. The phenomenon of organizational justice, which defines employees' evaluations of justice applied by managers within the organization (Greenberg, 1990: 403), was introduced with Adams' (1963, 1965) equality theory. According to the theory, people compare the rewards they get from their efforts and work with the rewards others get, and monitor the extent to which the rewards deemed appropriate for them are equal to those of individuals with similar achievements (Taris et al., 2002). These comparisons are made based on criteria such as vacation, social rights, wages, and working overtime. The sense of fairness of employees, which is the most important element of organizations, is not limited only by these criteria. In general, they want all employees to benefit from the rights and responsibilities in a fair way (Ayan et al., 2014: 394). It is also possible to explain organizational justice with the exchange theory. According to this theory, not only equality among employees is taken into account, but employees evaluate what they receive against what they give. In other words, they compare their educational level, skills, experience, and efforts in the organization with their achievements (Mullins, 2007: 126-135). The high perception of justice in an organization shows the importance that the organization attaches to its employees. If the employees have a strong sense of justice towards the organization, since they feel themselves as a valuable part of the organization, their loyalty to the company will increase, and employees will work more in harmony with their managers (Skarlicki and Folger, 1997: 435; Fischer, 2004: 488).

The concept of organizational justice is discussed in three main dimensions as distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice in the literature. Distributive justice compares acquisitions which the organization offers with employees' organizational responsibilities, their professional areas of work, the level of performance they perform, and other work-related effects (Moorman, 1991: 848). Another definition of distributive justice is the equitable application of wage or working conditions, social rights, performance transmission, and rank chances to the employees of the organization (Özdevecioğlu, 2003: 78). Procedural justice; determines the level of fairness in the processes, styles, standards, and practices used in the selection and evaluation of the factors such salary, promotion in office, physical facilities, business conditions, and performance measurement etc. (Demirel, 2009: 121). Distributive justice is related to fair perception of results; procedural justice concerns the perception that people can participate in the process when decisions are made, and that decisions are taken impartial and objectively (Moon et al., 2008: 85). Since individuals are sensitive to the treatment they are exposed, employees' negative perceptions related to procedural justice cause them to lower their performance and reduce their commitment to managers and organizations (İşbaşı, 2000: 52).

The perception of an unfair situation by employees in organizations leads to negative behaviors (Beugre, 1998: 1092; Bernardin and Cooke, 1993: 1098). The most effective outcome of employees' perceptions of justice is turnover intention. Employees' feeling of inequality between the way they are treated compared with other employees in the organization, or thinking that they should be treated better, or disproportionate

working hours compared to the wages received are among the factors that increase the turnover intention (Gürpınar, 2006: 55; Baltacı et al., 2014: 365). To reduce this perception, the administrative unit should be prepared to provide accurate and complete information and consult with the majority of employees, prepare an environment in which employees have the right to criticize decisions, and behave honestly in the assigned tasks. The management should reveal the appropriate reasons for the decisions taken and should not neglect to be in constant interaction with employees.

Turnover intention characterizes the employee's tendency to leave the organization and is expressed as the most important sign of the act of leaving (Kanten, 2014: 14). Factors that are closely related to work and cause employees to leave their jobs are the factors that researchers have focused on intensively. Job-related factors are generally economic reasons, autonomy, mediocrity at work, emotional exhaustion, support from coworkers, manager support, job risk, and fairness. In addition to these factors, role conflict arising from changes in the behaviors and practical actions required of employees, lack of detailed information on how the work process should be carried out, lack of clear understanding of the level of expectations of managers, and high pressure from other employees and organizations are also work-related factors (Kula et al., 2015: 133).

When various studies on organizational justice and turnover intention are examined in the literature, it is understood that organizational justice perception is effective on turnover intention (Owolabi, 2012; Örucü and Özafşarlıoğlu, 2013; Sokhanvar et al., 2016; Kang and Sung, 2019; Tolukan and Akyel, 2019; Mengstie, 2020; Anthoniammal et al., 2022; Choi and Shin, 2022; Özkan, 2023). According to the research results, as employees become aware of the principles and goals of the organization they work for and their sense of belonging, the ethical consciousness they think about not leaving the organization increases strongly and leads to a decrease in their tendency to leave their jobs (Çakar and Ceylan, 2005; Kang and Sung, 2019; Mengstie, 2020). In particular, perceived distributive and procedural justice has come to the fore as important factors affecting the turnover intention. It has been concluded that these two sub-dimensions of organizational justice have a negative relationship with the tendency to leave the workplace (Gürpınar, 2006; Anthoniammal et al., 2022). As a result, it has been decided to establish hypothesis H₁ based on the idea that turnover intention may be an inevitable event among Turkish employees in Germany who could be treated unfairly in the organization due to their differences.

H₁: Perceived organizational justice has a negative effect on employees' turnover intention.

Organizational Exclusion and Turnover Intention

Organizational exclusion is defined as the exclusion, non-acceptance, or disapproval of a person or group by another person or group (Balliet and Ferris, 2013: 30). The concept of exclusion in working life is reflected in non-participation in the labor force or abandonment of the labor market and discrimination in the workplace environment (Çakır, 2008: 27). In this case, colleagues may not want to have lunch with excluded colleagues, may be indifferent to their input in the decision-making process or may refuse to greet them. It is argued that the exclusion of the person within the organization prevents the will to develop or maintain positive relationships between individuals and their work-related achievements (Balliet and Ferris, 2013: 302). Although it is common in working conditions, the most important problem that we do not often see in the field of organizational behavior is exclusion. Organizational exclusion is a difficult problem to prove because in most cases it is done intentionally to implement a plan, in some cases it is unintentional and sloppy, and unfortunately in many cases it cannot be proven. In some cases, employees feel that they are subjected to organizational discrimination in every negative situation they face (Orhan, 2015: 175).

Organizational exclusion is based on social pain theory. The theory refers to a specific emotional response to the perception that one is excluded from desirable relationships or devalued by desirable relationship

partners or groups. Decline in relationships refers to the perception of feeling less valued by friends or other group members (MacDonald and Leary, 2005). In this case, the individual has the thought of quitting the job as a defensive attitude against the psychological distress caused by exclusion (Ferris et al., 2008). With the idea of leaving work, an individual can relieve the needs he has lost due to exclusion -such as belonging, feeling valuable, and making life meaningful- by meeting them in another organization (Maner et al, 2007). Therefore, studies conducted measure the relationship between organizational exclusion and turnover intention (O'Reilly et al., 2015; Soybalı and Pelit, 2018; Köllen et al., 2020; Köksal et al., 2021). As a result of the studies, some negative effects of organizational exclusion on employee behaviors have been identified. In this regard, Baumeister and Tice (1990), Chow et al. (2008), Finne et al. (2011), and Wu et al. (2011) found that organizational exclusion resulted in anxiety, depression, social anxiety, embarrassment, low self-esteem, job dissatisfaction due to irritability, decreased organizational commitment, and eventually turnover intention. When these studies and other research results were evaluated together, it was decided to establish H₂ within the scope of the study.

H₂: Perceived organizational exclusion has a positive effect on employees' turnover intention.

When information in the literature is evaluated, it is seen that organizational justice and turnover intention (Örücü and Özafşarlıoğlu, 2013; Tourani et al., 2016; Sokhanvar et al., 2016; Mengstie, 2020), organizational exclusion and turnover intention (Cottingham et al., 2013; Soybalı and Pelit, 2018; Köksal et al., 2021), and organizational justice and exclusion (İzci, 2018) variables are studied together with binary combinations. However, there is no study in which organizational justice, turnover intention, and organizational exclusion variables are examined together. It is thought that this study, in which these three variables are examined together, will put up to expanding and enriching the subject in a relational context. Hence, this research assumes that investigating the mediating the role of organizational exclusion in addressing the relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention will contribute to the literature and enhance the methodological approach used in this study. In this context, the following hypothesis H₃ was developed.

H₃: Perceived organizational exclusion has a mediating role in the effect of perceived organizational justice on turnover intention.

In the study on organizational justice, turnover intention, and organizational exclusion among Turkish employees in food production factories in Germany; the research model depicted in Figure-1 was developed based on the literature to test the mediating role of organizational exclusion in the effect of organizational justice on turnover intention. The three research hypotheses developed to test the proposed research model are shown on the model.

Figure-1: Research Model

METHOD

The research is handled with the quantitative method. In this context, a field study was conducted to examine the effect of organizational justice perception on turnover intention and the mediating role of organizational exclusion on this effect. Since the purpose of the research is to determine the cause-effect relationships among the variables, the research is descriptive in nature.

Sample and Procedure

A field study was conducted to test the research hypotheses. In this context, the population of the research consists of food factories in Germany and the sample of the research consists of Turkish employees working in food factories in Lübeck city in the State of Schleswig Holstein, Germany. According to the Statistical Office North, 4270 Turkish people live in the hanseatic city of Lübeck (Statistical Office, 2021). To find out the number of Turks actively working in the city, the Lübeck employment agency was contacted, but due to the data privacy policy, the number of Turkish employees could not be obtained. Based on the assumption that all 4270 Turks living in Lübeck cannot be employees, the sample of the study was determined as 327 people with a 5% margin of error in a 95% confidence interval (Sekaran, 1992: 253). As a data collection tool, the survey technique was used in the research. Using the purposive sampling method, 400 questionnaires were distributed to Turkish employees working in Erasco, Mayo Feinkost, Campbell's, Hela, Wilhelm Schumacher GmbH, Peter Steffen GmbH, Continental Foods, Abakus Group, Anker GmbH, Artur Heymann GmbH & Co, and Hawesta companies. After the necessary explanations were made by the researchers, in the end, 345 completely filled and evaluable questionnaires were obtained.

When the demographic distribution of the Turkish employees attending in the research according to gender, marital status, age, educational level, and working time is examined; 39.1% of the 345 employees are male and 60.9% are female. 51.6% of them are single and 48.4% are married. Most of the participants (62.6%) are between the ages of 35-50, 28.3% are between the ages of 50-65, and 10.1% are 25-35. Considering the educational status, 42.2% of the participants graduated from secondary school, 26.1% graduated from high school and 32.7% graduated from elementary school. The study period of 55.8% of the participants varies between 10-15 years.

Measures

Within the scope of the research, the scales of organizational justice, turnover intention, and organizational exclusion, whose validity and reliability have been tested by many studies, were used. The research employed a questionnaire comprising of four sections. In the first section, there are 5 questions aimed at determining the socio-demographic characteristics of the employees. In the second section, there are 20 statements that assess the perception of organizational justice. To assess the level of perceived organizational justice, the organizational justice perception scale developed by Niehoff and Moorman (1993) was utilized. The third section includes 5 statements to measure employees' turnover intentions. To reach these statements, Walsh et al.'s turnover intention scale (Harputoğlu, 2015: 54) was used. Finally, the fourth section includes 6 statements measuring the level of organizational exclusion. To reach these statements, an adaptation was made using the organizational exclusion scale developed by Ferris. et al. (2008). The questionnaire consists of 31 statements and 5 demographic questions. The statements were prepared in the form of a 5-point Likert scale.

Data Analysis Procedure

The analysis of the research data was made using the SPSS quantitative data statistical analysis program. First, the collected data were reviewed to make them suitable for analysis. In this context, the scales were

subjected to reliability analysis, and then factor analysis and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test were performed respectively to divide the organizational justice scale into sub-dimensions. To test the research hypotheses, correlation analysis was conducted to examine whether there exist notable relationships among employees' perceived organizational justice, organizational exclusion, and turnover intention levels. Afterwards, regression analysis was used to measure the effects of employees' perceptions of organizational justice and feelings of exclusion on their turnover intention. Finally, to analyze the mediating effect, the causal step approach known as the "Baron and Kenney" method (1986) was used.

FINDINGS AND EVALUATION OF THE RESEARCH

Factor and Reliability Analysis

In the multidimensional organizational justice scale used in the study, factor analysis was used to determine the relevant sub-dimensions of the organizational justice perception. The turnover intention and organizational exclusion perception scales were not subjected to factor analysis since they were originally created as single dimension scales and the number of statements was low. The relevance of the organizational justice scale to the factor analysis was tested and since the result obtained from the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (K.M.O) test was 0.869 and $p < 0,05$, it was determined to be appropriate for the factor analysis. The explanatory factor analysis table of the scales is given in Table-1 below.

Table-1: Explanatory Factor Analysis

Explanatory Factor Analysis of Perceived Organizational Justice Scale			Factor Weights		
Factors	Items		1	2	3
Distributive Justice	13. When decisions are taken about my job, I am treated with dignity and my opinions are valued.		,781		
			,714		
	12. When decisions are taken about my job, my manager is concerned and nice to me.		,691		
	17. My managers discuss the consequences of decisions about my job with me.		,628		
	15. When decisions are taken about my job, managers behave sincere and honest towards me.		,636		
	16. When decisions are taken about my job, managers supervise my rights.		,620		
	19. When decisions are taken about my job, managers provide justifiable explanations.		,618		
	20. My managers explain every decision about my work clearly to me.		,577		
	18. My managers show reasonable justifications for decisions about work.		,481		
	10. All business choices are implemented without discrimination to all affected employees.				
Interactional Justice	4. I think that the achievements I get from my workplace are fair when seen as a whole.			,710	
	8. Managers collect complete and precise information before making job decisions.			,633	
	7. Managers get the views of all employees before taking decisions about work.			,644	
	6. Decisions regarding work are taken in an unbiased way by the managers.			,618	
	9. Managers communicate their decisions to employees and offer supplementary information upon request.			,591	
	3. I believe that my workload is fair.			,576	

	11. Employees may oppose the business-related decisions of managers, or may request that these are revised by higher authorities.	,528
Procedural Justice	2. I believe that my fee is fair.	,674
	1. I believe that my work schedule is fair.	,644
	5. I think that my work duties are fair.	,597
	14. Managers are responsive to my personal demands while making decisions about my job.	,493
KMO and Bartlett's Test (Bartlett's Test of Sphericity)		
	Kasier-Mayer-Olkin Sample adequacy = 0,869	
	Approximately Ki-Square = 959,587	
	Df (degree of freedom) = 190	
	p = ,000	

As a result of the applied factor analysis, the sub-dimensions of perceived organizational justice are gathered in three factors as distributive, interactional and procedural justice perceptions. When the factor loads of these factors are analyzed, it is seen that they are above 0.4, which is the acceptable limit for social sciences (Şencan, 2005: 390). Therefore, the factor loadings of the items given in Table-2 are statistically sufficient.

Table-2: Reliability Analysis Results for Scales and Sub-Dimensions

Scales and Subdimensions	Cronbach's Alpha
Organizational Justice	,897
<i>Distributive Justice</i>	,781
<i>Interactional Justice</i>	,823
<i>Procedural Justice</i>	,768
Turnover Intention	,665
Organizational Exclusion	,917

These values show the reliability levels of the expressions in the scales. Reliability analysis “is a method developed to evaluate the characteristics and reliability of tests, questionnaires, or scales used in measurement” (Kalaycı, 2014: 403). If the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than or equal to 0.70, the scale is considered reliable. In social sciences, however, this boundary is accepted as 0.60 and above as well (Sipahi et al., 2008: 89). In this context, when the reliability coefficients of the relevant scale and sub-dimensions are examined; the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of organizational justice, turnover intention, and organizational exclusion scales and subscales is adequate. This means that the dimensions and sub-dimensions of the expressions are clearly understood by the participants.

Correlation Analysis

To test whether there is a meaningful relationship among the levels of employees' perceived organizational justice, organizational exclusion, and turnover intention, findings in Table-3 were obtained as a result of the correlation analysis conducted.

Table-3: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Coefficients Related to Variables

Scales	Mean*	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Organizational Justice (1)	3,04	,658	1				
- Distributive Justice (2)	2,93	,771	,807**	1			
- Procedural Justice (3)	2,85	,728	,826**	,634**	1		
- Interactional Justice (4)	3,23	,797	,921**	,608**	,655**	1	
Organizational Exclusion (5)	2,67	,969	-,389**	-,289**	-,259**	-,453**	1

Turnover Intention	3,30	,749	-,161	-137	-,155	-,122	-,132
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*In the scale; 1= «Absolutely Disagree» 5 = «Absolutely Participate»
** Correlation is significant at the 0,01 level (two-tailed). p<0,01 (n=345)

According to the results of correlation analysis; There is a moderately negative and statistically significant relationship between participants’ organizational justice and organizational exclusion levels ($r = -0,389$; $p < 0,01$). In addition, negative and significant relationships were found among distributive justice, procedural justice, interactive justice, and organizational exclusion (distributive justice: $r = -0,289$, procedural justice: $r = -0,259$, interactive justice: $r = -0,453$; , $p < 0,01$). Significant relationships were not found among the participants’ organizational justice levels and subscales, and turnover intention ($p > 0,05$). Finally, no significant relationship was found between organizational exclusion and turnover intention ($p > 0,05$).

Regression Analysis

To test the effects of the employees’ perceptions of organizational justice on their turnover intention and to test the mediating role of organizational exclusion in this relationship, hierarchical regression analysis proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986) was performed. First of all, in the simple linear regression analysis, it is seen that the necessary conditions for Baron and Kenny’s mediation relationship are met. According to this; it seems that the organizational justice variable, which is the independent variable, has a significant and negative effect on organizational exclusion, which is the mediating variable ($\beta = -0,43$), and turnover intention ($\beta = -0,22$), which is the dependent variable. In this context, the results of the hierarchical regression analysis to test the mediator effect can be seen as follows in Table-4.

Table-4: Hierarchical Regression Analysis

Model	Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	B	Beta	T	R	R ²	ΔR^2	F	p
1	Turnover Intention	Org. Exclusion	-0,11	-0,09	-0,84	0,78	0,007	-0,00	0,69	0,416
2	Org. Exclusion	Org. Justice	-0,59	-0,43	-4,82	0,43	0,19	0,15	21,93	0,000
3	Turnover Intention	Org. Justice	-0,25	-0,22	-2,21	0,23	0,043	0,031	4,81	0,039
4	Turnover Intention	Org. Justice	-0,33	-0,30	-2,81	0,29	0,071	0,053	4,30	0,008
		Org. Exclusion	-0,16	-0,18	-1,95					0,055

According to the results of the hierarchical regression analysis, it can be seen that organizational justice perception has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention ($\beta = -0,22$; $p = 0,039$; Model 3). In this context, the hypothesis H_1 is accepted. According to Table-4, there is no significant effect of employees’ perception of organizational exclusion on turnover intention ($\beta = -0,09$; $p = 0,416$; $p > 0,05$; Model 1). In this direction the hypothesis H_2 was rejected. When the mediating effect is examined according to model 3, it is obvious that the effect of perceived organizational justice on turnover intention is $\beta = -0,22$, whereas the mediating effect of organizational exclusion has an increased negative effect ($\beta = -0,30$; Model 4). This is not supported by Baron and Kenny’s (1986) mediating relationship “when the effect of the mediating variable is controlled, the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable is decreasing or disappearing”; as the independent variable increases the effect on the dependent variable when the mediator is included in the model. Moreover, it was observed that the mediating effect of organizational exclusion was not statistically significant ($\beta = -0,18$; $p = 0,055$). As a result, it can be said that the employees’ perceived organizational

exclusion doesn't have a mediating role on the influence of perceived organizational justice on employees' turnover intention. In this context, the hypothesis H₃ has been rejected.

CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the mediating role of organizational exclusion in the effect of perceived organizational justice on turnover intention was tried to be determined. In this context, it is aimed to investigate the tendency of Turkish employees working in food factories in the city of Lübeck in Schleswig Holstein, a State of Germany to quit their jobs when they encounter an unfair attitude in their working life and the mediating effect of organizational exclusion. With the results obtained from the study, it is also aimed to contribute to the literature.

According to the results of the correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship and direction between the variables, a negative relationship was found between employees' perceptions of organizational justice and organizational exclusion. In other words, it can be said that as the perception of organizational justice increases, the perception of exclusion decreases, and as the perception of organizational justice decreases, the perception of exclusion increases. In addition, negative relationships were found among the sub-dimensions of organizational justice (distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice) and organizational exclusion. No significant relationship was found among participants' organizational justice levels and its sub-dimensions and turnover intention. Finally, no significant relationship was found between organizational exclusion and turnover intention.

Based on the results of the hierarchical regression analysis conducted to test the hypotheses of the study; it is clear that organizational justice perception has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. In other words, the organizational justice perceptions of Turkish employees in Germany negatively affect their turnover intention with all sub-dimensions. This finding is in line with the findings of similar studies in the literature (Çakar and Ceylan, 2005; Gürpınar, 2006; Özer and Günlük, 2010; Owolabi, 2012; Tolukan and Akyel, 2019; Kang and Sung, 2019; Mengstie, 2020; Anthoniammal et al., 2022; Choi and Shin, 2022). In some studies, different results were obtained in the sub-dimensions of organizational justice. In a study conducted in the United States, procedural justice had a significant negative relationship with turnover intention, but distributive justice had a non-significant relationship (Lambert et al., 2023). Sokhanvar et al. (2016) observed a significant inverse correlation among turnover intention and organizational justice, interactional justice, and procedural justice; but no relationship was found among turnover intention and systemic and distributive justice types.

In addition to these findings, it has been determined that employees' perception of organizational exclusion does not have a significant effect on turnover intention. It was also found that organizational exclusion perceived by Turkish employees in Germany does not have a mediating role in the effect of perceived organizational justice on turnover intention. These findings are not parallel or similar to the results of other studies in the literature. Previous studies have shown that organizational exclusion perceived by employees leads to anxiety, depression, social anxiety, embarrassment, low self-esteem, job dissatisfaction due to irritability, decreased organizational commitment, and eventually turnover intention (Baumeister and Tice, 1990; Chow et al., 2008; Finne et al., 2011; Wu et al., 2011; Cottingham et al., 2013; Soybalı and Pelit, 2018; Köllen et al., 2020; Köksal et al., 2021; Korman et al., 2021). Contrary to these findings, in this study conducted on Turkish employees in Germany, it was revealed that perceived organizational exclusion did not have any significant effect on turnover intention. It is thought that there are various reasons for these results that differ from the literature. One of the most important reasons is thought to be cultural context and social support. It is known that there is a strong social support network among Turkish employees in Germany. The support network formed among employees within the same firm may reduce the impact of negative

experiences in the workplace. Cultural ties and family support, however, may reduce turnover intention. In addition, Germany is a country with high job security. Job security can reduce employees' turnover intention. When the risk of job loss is low, the impact of factors such as organizational exclusion on turnover intention may decrease. Another factor may be workplace diversity and exclusion policies. In particular, workplaces that employ foreign workers may follow policies that are sensitive to exclusion and discrimination. In such workplaces, the impact of organizational exclusion may be reduced because management may make efforts to mitigate such experiences of employees.

Theoretical Implications

This study, which measures the perceptions of organizational justice, turnover intention and organizational exclusion of employees in food factories in Germany, is thought to make some contributions to both the literature and the methodology. Although the variables in question have been frequently investigated before, it is thought that this study offers a new perspective to the research field by bringing together issues such as perceived organizational justice, turnover intention and organizational exclusion. This is because the variables have been investigated in binary combinations, but it has not been found that the three variables have been studied together. This type of article can form the basis for future research by expanding the literature on the subject. Other researchers can use the results and approaches of this paper to take the topic further. Moreover, such issues are important factors affecting relationships, motivation and commitment in the workplace. Therefore, this kind of paper can make an important contribution to understanding the fundamental aspects of organizational behavior. In addition, the model proposal used in this article and the methodological approaches developed to examine complex relationships can serve as a guide for similar studies in the future.

Practical Implications

In addition to the theoretical and methodological contributions of the research, it is thought to offer some contributions to business managers and employees. By emphasizing the mediating role of organizational exclusion in the relationship between perceived organizational justice and turnover intention, the article can guide managers and leaders to develop more effective strategies. These strategies aim to increase employees' commitment and motivation to the organization. By explaining the effects of perceived organizational justice and organizational exclusion on turnover intention, organizations can develop better strategies to increase employees' job satisfaction and strengthen their commitment to the organization. These strategies can be geared towards making employees feel more valued and integrated within the organization. Also, the findings presented in this paper may provide an opportunity for human resource departments to review and improve their policies and practices in order to reduce turnover intentions and ensure that employees have a more positive experience within the organization. Moreover, the findings presented in the paper may inspire managers and leaders to create training and development programs to enhance organizational justice and minimize organizational exclusion. Such programs can support managers and employees to improve their communication skills and prevent negative behaviors.

Limitations and Future Research

The research is limited to organizational justice, turnover intention, and organizational exclusion variables. In addition, the fact that the research was conducted in a certain city within a given period of time constitutes another limitation of the research. First of all, it may be recommended to conduct similar studies in more industrial cities rather than in small cities such as Lübeck. To make generalizations, it is suggested that future studies should be conducted with more appropriate and larger samples. In addition, it should be taken into account that the study is evaluated only on the data of a certain period of time. Considering the foreign policies of countries periodically, it can be said that it would be a more appropriate approach to conduct

studies continuously. Conducting similar studies on different nationalities, different ethnic groups, and refugees in various countries would enrich the information obtained and provide a broader perspective. It should not be forgotten that individuals have different qualities from each other because they are born with different religions, languages, and ethnic origins. Instead of seeing these differences as superior to one another, one should focus on the fact that people have complementary qualities, and instead of excluding or confronting individuals, it should be brought up the need to live together and share. In this context, in addition to the above mentioned suggestions, it is highly recommended to study the issue of “diversity management” in the sample of foreign nationals or refugees in addition to the variables within the scope of this study.

REFERENCES

- Adams, J.S. (1963). Toward an understanding of inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67 (5), 422-436.
- Adams, J.S. (1965). Inequity in social exchange. In *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*. Berkowitz, L. (Ed.), Academic Press, New York, NY, 267-299.
- Anthoniammal, A., Arul, M., and Sakthivel, D. (2022). Organizational justice, turnover intention and employees job performance, a co-relation study. 1067-1075.
- Ayan, M., Aşkın, S., and Arslan, S. (2014). Çalışanların örgütsel adalet ve örgütsel bağlılık algıları üzerine bir araştırma. 2. *Örgütsel Davranış Kongresi Bildiriler Kitabı*, 15546 (978-605-86838-4-6), 389-415.
- Balliet, D. and Ferris, D. L. (2013). Ostracism and prosocial behavior: A social dilemma perspective. *Organizational Behavior And Human Decision Processes*, 120(2), 298-308.
- Baltacı, F., Güçlü, C., and Çeliker, N. (2014). Liderlik davranışının örgütsel adalet algısı ve işten ayrılma niyeti üzerine etkileri: Konaklama işletmelerinde bir uygulama. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 19(3), 353-370.
- Baron, R. M., and Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51, 1173–1182.
- Baumeister, R. F., and Tice, D. M. (1990). Point-counterpoints: Anxiety and social exclusion. *Journal of social and clinical psychology*, 9(2), 165-195.
- Bernardin, H. J., and Cooke, D.K. (1993). Validity of an honesty test in predicting theft among convenience store employees. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(5), 1097-1108.
- Beugre C.D. (1998). *Managing Fairness in Organizations*. Greenwood Publishing Group, Incorporated, Quorum Books Westport, Connecticut, London.
- Choi, H. and Shin, S. (2022). The factors that affect turnover intention according to clinical experience: a focus on organizational justice and nursing core competency. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(6), 3515.
- Chow, R. M., Tiedens, L. Z., and Govan, C. L. (2008). Excluded emotions: the role of anger in antisocial responses to ostracism. *Journal Of Experimental Social Psychology*, 44(3), 896-903.
- Cottingham, M. D., Erickson, R. J., Diefendorff, J. M., and Bromley, G. (2013). The effect of manager exclusion on nurse turnover intention and care quality. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 35(8), 970-985.
- Çakar, N. D., and Ceylan, A. (2005). İş motivasyonunun çalışan bağlılığı ve işten ayrılma eğilimi üzerindeki etkileri. *Doğuş Üniversitesi Dergisi*, 6(1), 52-66.
- Çakır, Ö. (2008). Türkiye’de kadının çalışma yaşamından dışlanması. *Erciyes Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi* (31), 25-47.

- Demirel, Y. (2009). Örgütsel bağlılık ve üretkenlik karşıtı davranışlar arasındaki ilişkiye kavramsal yaklaşım. *Istanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 8(15), 115-132.
- Ferris, D. L., Brown, D. J., Berry, J. W., and Lian, H. (2008). The development and validation of the workplace ostracism scale. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 6, 1348-1366.
- Finne, L. B., Knardahl, S., and Lau, B. (2011). Workplace bullying and mental distress—A prospective study of Norwegian employees. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 276-287.
- Fischer, R. (2004). Rewarding employee loyalty: An organizational justice approach. *International Journal Of Organizational Behavior*, 8(3), 486-503.
- Greenberg, J. (1990). Organizational justice: Yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *Journal of Management*, 16(2), 399-432.
- Gürpınar, G. (2006). An empirical study of relationships among organizational justice, organizational commitment, leader-member exchange, and turnover intention. *Yeditepe University Social Sciences Enstitute, Unpublished Master's Thesis, İstanbul*.
- Haq, I. U. (2014). Workplace ostracism and job outcomes: Moderating effects of psychological capital. In *Human Capital Without Borders: Knowledge and Learning for Quality of Life: Proceedings of The Management, Knowledge and Learning International Conference, Örebro, Sweden: ToKnowPress*.
- Harputoğlu, D. D. (2015). İşe tutkunluk ve iş-aile-iş çatışmasının işten ayrılma niyetine etkisi: Konaklama işletmelerinde bir uygulama. *Çanakkale On Sekiz Mart University Social Sciences Enstitute, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Çanakkale*.
- İzci, Ç. (2018). Akademik kurumlarda örgütsel adalet ve dışlanma ilişkisi: Araştırma görevlileri üzerine bir araştırma. *Trakya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*. 20(2), 177-194.
- İşbaşı, J. (2000). Çalışanların yöneticilere duydukları güvenin ve örgütsel adalete ilişkin algılamalarının örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışının oluşumundaki rolü: Bir turizm örgütünde uygulama. *Akdeniz University Social Sciences Enstitute, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Antalya*.
- Kalaycı, Ş. (2014). *Spss uygulamaları çok değişkenli istatistik teknikleri* (6th Edition). Asil Yayınevi.
- Kang, M. and Sung, M. (2019). To leave or not to leave: the effects of perceptions of organizational justice on employee turnover intention via employee-organization relationship and employee job engagement. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 31(5-6), 152-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1062726X.2019.1680988>
- Kanten, P. (2014). İşyeri nezaketsizliğinin sosyal kaytarma davranışı ve işten ayrılma niyeti üzerindeki etkisinde duygusal tükenmenin aracılık rolü. *Aksaray Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 6(1), 11-26.
- Korman, B. A., Tröster, C., and Giessner, S. R. (2021). The consequences of incongruent abusive supervision: Anticipation of social exclusion, shame, and turnover intentions. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 28(3), 306-321.
- Köksal, K., Gürsoy, A., and Yusuf, T. U. T. A. (2021). Aile desteğinin örgütsel dışlanma ile işten ayrılma niyeti ilişkisindeki rolü. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 17(35), 1925-1945.
- Köllen, T., Koch, A., and Hack, A. (2020). Nationalism at work: Introducing the “nationality-based organizational climate inventory” and Assessing its impact on the turnover intention of foreign employees. *Manag Int Rev* 60, 97–122, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11575-019-00408-4>
- Kula, S., Taşdöven, H., and Dönmez, M. (2015). The impacts of education, vocational tenure and career opportunities on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and intent to leave. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 12(1), 129-149.
- Lambert, E. G., Solinas-Saunders, M., Haynes, S. H., May, D. C., Keena, L. D., Leone, M., and Buckner, Z. (2023). The association of organizational justice views and turnover intent among correctional staff. *Criminal Justice Studies*, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1478601X.2023.2239994>

- Lyu, Y. and Zhu, H. (2019). The predictive effects of workplace ostracism on employee attitudes: A job embeddedness perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(8), 1083–1095.
- MacDonald G and Leary MR. (2005). Why does social exclusion hurt? The relationship between social and physical pain. *Psychological Bulletin.*;131(2), 202. doi:10.1037/0033-2909.131.2.202.
- Maner, J. K., DeWall, C. N., Baumeister, R. F., and Schaller, M. (2007). Does social exclusion motivate interpersonal reconnection? Resolving the porcupine problem. *J. Pers. Soc. Psychol.*, 92, 42–55. doi:10.1037/e633962013-015
- Mengstie, M. M. (2020). Perceived organizational justice and turnover intention among hospital healthcare workers. *BMC psychology*, 8, 1-11.
- Moon, H., Kamdar D., Mayer D.M., and Takeuchi R. (2008). Me or we? The role of personality and justice as other-centered antecedents to innovative citizenship behaviors within organizations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93 (1).
- Moorman, R. H. (1991). Relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviors: Do fairness perceptions influence employee citizenship?. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(6), 845-855.
- Mullins L. J. (2007). *Management and organisational behaviour* (8th ed.). Harlow: FT Prentice Hall.
- Niehoff, B. P. and Moorman, R. H. (1993). Justice as a mediator of the relationship between methods of monitoring and organizational citizenship behavior. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(3), 527-556.
- O'Reilly, J., Robinson, S. L., Berdahl, J. L., and Banki, S. (2015). Is negative attention better than no attention? The comparative effects of ostracism and harassment at work. *Organ. Sci.*, 26, 774-793. doi:10.1287/orsc.2014.0900
- Orhan, U. (2015). Sosyal gerçeklik mi, algı mı? Almanya'daki Türklerin işyerinde ırksal ayrımcılık deneyimleri üzerine bir çalışma. *Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 25(1), 175-183.
- Owolabi, A. B. (2012). Effect of organizational justice and organizational environment on turn-over intention of health workers in Ekiti state, Nigeria. *Research in World Economy*, 3(1), 28-34.
- Örücü, E. and Özafşarlıoğlu, S. (2013). Örgütsel adaletin çalışanların işten ayrılma niyetine etkisi: Güney Afrika Cumhuriyeti'nde bir uygulama. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 10(23), 335-358.
- Özdevecioğlu, M. (2003). Algılanan örgütsel adaletin bireylerarası saldırgan davranışlar üzerindeki etkilerinin belirlenmesine yönelik bir araştırma. *Erciyes Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*(21), 77-96.
- Özer, G. and Günlük, M. (2010). Örgütsel adaletin muhasebecilerin iş memnuniyeti ve işten ayrılma eğilimlerine etkisi. *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 9(2), 459-485.
- Özkan, A. H. (2023). Organizational justice perceptions and turnover intention: a meta-analytic review. *Kybernetes*, 52(8), 2886-2899.
- Sekaran, U. (1992). *Research methods for business – a skill building approach* (2nd Ed). United States of America: John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- Sipahi, B. Y., Yurtkoru, E. ES., and Çinko, M. (2008). *Sosyal bilimlerde SPSS'le veri analizi*. İstanbul: Beta Basım Yayım Dağıtım.
- Skarlicki, D. P. and Folger, R. (1997). Retaliation in the workplace: the roles of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 82(3),434-443. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.82.3.434>
- Sokhanvar M, Hasanpoor E, Hajihashemi S, and Kakemam E. (2016). The relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention: A survey on hospital nurses. *Patient Saf Qual Improv.*, 4(2), 358-362.

Soybalı, H. H. and Pelit, O. (2018). Örgütsel dışlanmanın işten ayrılma niyetine etkisi: Afyonkarahisar'daki beş yıldızlı otel işletmelerinde bir araştırma. *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 20(3), 225-249

Statistikamt (2021). Statistische Berichte statistisches Amt für Hamburg und Schleswig-Holstein, <https://www.statistik-nord.de>

Taris T. (2002). Inequity at work: its measurement and association with worker health. *Work & Stres*, 16(4), 287–301.

Tolukan, E. and Akyel, Y. (2019). Research on the relationship between trainers' turnover intention and organizational justice. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 8(1), 181-192.

Tourani, S., Khosravizadeh, O., Omrani, A., Sokhanvar, M., Kakemam, E., and Najafi, B. (2016). The relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention of hospital nurses in Iran. *Materia socio-medica*, 28(3), 205.

Wu, L., Wei, L., and Hui, C. (2011). Dispositional antecedents and consequences of workplace ostracism: An empirical examination. *Frontiers Of Business Research in China*, 5(1), 23-44.